

Supporting Information:

Guanidinium Like-Charge Ion Pairing and Oligoarginine Aggregation in Water by NMR, Cryo-Electron Microscopy, and Molecular Dynamics

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NMR Experiments

Figure S1: ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR shifts of GdmCl solution in neat water.

Figure S2: ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR shifts of GdmCl solution in the solution with 6 M ionic strength.

Quantum Mechanical Calculations

Figure S3: Optimized Gdm⁺–Gdm⁺ (top) and NH₄⁺–NH₄⁺ (bottom) dimers at B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory. Gdm⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions are depicted in blue and red colors, respectively, using QuickSurf visualization in VMD,^{S1} with these colors corresponding to the data lines in other figures for consistency.

Figure S4: The dependence of the ^{13}C -NMR chemical shift for the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer on the distance between guanidinium carbons. The data are calculated from quantum chemical calculations at the PCM/B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ level of accuracy.

Table S1: Predicted ^{13}C -NMR chemical shifts for the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer and Gdm^+ monomer, along with the corresponding differences, calculated using quantum mechanical methods with different levels of accuracy and solvent representations.

Method	Monomer [ppm]	Dimer [ppm]	Δ [ppm]
B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-cc-pVDZ	160.19	158.78	1.41
B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ	160.17	159.40	0.77
B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,p)//B3LYP-D3-6-31+G(d)	160.47	159.62	0.85

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Figure S5: Radial distribution functions $g_{\text{C}_z-\text{Cl}^-}(r)$ from MD simulations of GdmCl solutions at a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M. The data are presented only for the prosECCo75 force field, and the profiles are essentially identical. The same conclusions can be made from the profiles collected using the other tested force fields (KB and KB2, data not shown).

Table S2: Estimation of $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ binding free energy ΔG_b from MD simulations using different force fields and varying the total ionic strength and Gdm^+ concentration.

Force Field	Total / Gdm^+ Concentration [M]	ΔG_b [$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]
prosECCo75	3 / 0.1	-2.5
	3 / 3	-1.1
	6 / 0.5	-3.1
	6 / 6	-0.6
KB2	3 / 0.1	-1.4
	3 / 3	-0.6
	6 / 0.5	-1.7
	6 / 6	-0.4

Figure S6: Radial distribution functions $g_{C_z-C_z}(r)$ and $g_{N_z-N_z}(r)$ from MD simulations of GdmCl and NH_4Cl solutions, respectively, at a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M.

Figure S7: Potential of mean force calculated from the radial distribution functions from MD simulations of GdmCl solutions at a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M.

Figure S8: The ion pairing of the NH_4^+ cations as a function of NH_4^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic concentration of ~ 3 M is maintained by adding NaCl.

Figure S9: The ion pairing of the Gdm^+ cations as a function of Gdm^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic concentration of either ~ 3 M or ~ 6 M is maintained by adding NaCl.

CryoEM Experiments

Figure S10: (A) Representative cryo-EM images of 150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl₂ buffer, along with the corresponding binarized image used for autocorrelation function (ACF) calculation and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) power spectra derivation. The scale bar for cryo-EM image is 50 nm. (B) Comparison of radial profiles derived from FFT power spectra images of 100 mM R₉ (blue) and buffer-only samples (gray). (C) Comparison of radial profiles derived from FFT power spectra images of 100 mM K₉ (red) and buffer-only samples (gray). (D) Comparison of spatial ACFs measured from cryo-EM images of 100 mM R₉ (blue) and buffer-only solutions (gray). (E) Comparison of spatial ACFs measured from cryo-EM images of 100 mM K₉ (red) and buffer-only solutions (gray). Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation, based on $n = 205$ frames for R₉, $n = 152$ frames for K₉, and $n = 141$ frames for buffer-only samples.

References

- (S1) Humphrey, W.; Dalke, A.; Schulten, K. VMD: Visual molecular dynamics. *J. Mol. Graph.* **1996**, *14*, 33–38.